

INDICO & CITADEL SEARCH: A COLLABORATION CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Modern web applications, and content management systems, in particular, are expected to provide their users with simple and efficient methods to query data. While most modern relational databases do provide full-text indices, those are often not sufficient for rich querying of application contents, especially when compound queries are required. Moreover, they often provide mostly bare-bones functionality which has to be expanded on by the application developers. It does then pay off to offload full-text search on specialized systems which are capable of performing this task efficiently.

This paper introduces one such system, the *Citadel Search* service, and documents an attempt to use it to provide an efficient, transparent and open-source search solution for *Indico* - an open-source tool for event organisation, archival and collaboration built at CERN and deployed around the world.

For many years, *Indico* provided no out-of-the-box search engine and instances relied on locally-developed custom search strategies or services, often based on paid enterprise solutions, to fulfil this gap. At CERN, a proprietary search implementation based on *Sharepoint Search*¹ was used. Proven useful in the past, as it relieved the service from the complexity of maintaining an external search engine, it had the downside of not being reusable by the community and being based on a commercial product, which limited its affordability.

With more than 10 million documents at CERN, including events, attachments and metadata, *Indico* needed not only to preserve the quality of the existing search functionality, but also provide long-requested improvements on it, such as, better quality of results and a native interface.

Citadel Search is an open-source enterprise search solution that makes use of state of the art technologies such as *Elasticsearch*², *Tika*³ and the *Invenio Framework*⁴ for large-scale digital repositories. It is used by several large document collections at CERN, namely CERN's Engineering Data Management Service (EDMS), and by CERN's large information space made of more than 14000 Web sites.

Since it was announced [1], the major highlight was the addition of a new content extraction Application Programming Interface (API) - using *Tika* and *Celery* workers, and deployment templating of *Citadel* instances with *Helm*⁵, simplifying the adoption for new users.

Citadel focuses on transparency, efficiency and empowering its "user systems" by giving them control over their data and associated querying strategies. Built with collaboration in mind, it strives to offer to users a flexible solution for structured searching with document level Access Control Lists (ACLs), and structured data obtained with a web crawler. Custom-tailored data models can be created for different information sources, and fine grain access control is provided, as to obtain relevant results to search queries.

Our approach details how *Indico* overcame the challenges involved in designing a new search module on top of *Citadel*, adapting several heterogeneous records into structured documents, namely: events, contributions and materials. In addition, we explain how the search engine was adapted to cover multiple use-cases from a simple text-based search to advanced aggregations and filters.

¹ <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/sharepoint/dev/general-development/search-in-sharepoint>

² <https://www.elastic.co/what-is/elasticsearch>

³ <https://tika.apache.org/>

⁴ <https://inveniosoftware.org/>

⁵ <https://helm.sh/>

REFERENCES

- [1] *Citadel Search: Open Source Enterprise Search*, Open Search Symposium 2019, Garching / Munich, Germany, Oct. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3581157>